

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE CHARACTERISTICS AND THE
TOUGHENING MECHANISM OF A NEW GRAPHITE/BMI COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The interlaminar fracture characteristics of a graphite/bismaleimide composite prepared by using a new modified BMI matrix were investigated by various methods. Laminates of three typical stacking sequences were evaluated. Double cantilever beam and end-notch flexure tests were conducted under conventional conditions and in a scanning electron microscope. The fracture energy release rates G_{IC} and G_{IIC} have been determined and compared with the corresponding values for laminates with conventional matrices. A significant improvement in toughness was observed for the laminate with modified BMI matrix. Dynamic delamination propagation was studied. The toughening mechanism was discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

The damage failure modes of composite laminates mainly include matrix cracking, delamination and fiber breakage. However, delamination (interlaminar debonding) is the most important process. Even if there are cracks in the matrix, the laminate can still sustain loads. Fibers are main load-bearing components, but fibers break mostly in the final stage. Nevertheless, from the initiation of the damage to the failure of the laminate, delamination propagation is the major factor. Thus, delamination would limit the application and service life of composite structures. Delamination can result from impact, compressive, transverse tensile and shear stresses. In the recent decade, some attention has been paid to the analysis and control of delamination and to the determination of the interlaminar fracture toughness. The critical interlaminar fracture toughness G_c is an important

parameter characterizing the toughness and delamination resistance of a composite and is commonly used in damage and fracture calculations. There are some studies^(1,2) on G_c of unidirectional composites, but very little work has been reported on the interlaminar fracture toughness of multidirectional laminates which is even more complex. It is thus important to find suitable methods to determine the interlaminar fracture toughness, to investigate the delamination propagation and to analyse the toughening mechanism on a microscopic basis.

Epoxy is the commonly used matrix in composites but it is limited by its low fracture toughness, low delamination resistance and poor performance in hot/wet environment. Epoxy can be toughened by the addition of rubber but its thermal resistance is significantly reduced. In recent years, bismaleimide resins with good thermal properties have been developed^(3,4). However, such materials are limited by their brittleness and processing difficulties. A new modified bismaleimide (MBMI) has been recently produced⁽⁵⁾. This material possesses good toughness, higher thermal resistance, good processability and other excellent properties.

This paper is concerned with the interlaminar fracture characteristics of a graphite/bismaleimide composite prepared by using this new modified BMI matrix. The interlaminar fracture toughness and delamination propagation of three typical lay-up laminates were evaluated. Double cantilever beam (DCB for mode I- G_{Ic}) and end-notch flexure (ENF for mode II- G_{IIc}) tests were conducted under conventional conditions and in a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The fracture energy release rates G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} have been determined and compared with the corresponding values obtained for laminates with conventional matrices. A significant improvement in toughness was found for the laminates with modified BMI matrix. Delamination occurrence and propagation in laminates have been observed in real time by dynamic scanning electron microscopy. In addition, the toughening mechanism was discussed.

2. SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The test specimens were machined from panels made of T300 graphite fibers in a modified bismaleimide (MBMI) matrix. The fiber volume fraction V_f was 60-61%. The matrix was a commercially available bismaleimide modified by compounding with PES. MBMI was dissolved in a low boiling point solvent. T300 graphite fiber unidirectional prepreg was made by the solvent method. The composites were cured at 177°C under a standard low autoclave of 5 bar pressure for 2 hours, then moved into an oven for post curing at 120°C for 5 hours. The thickness of each ply was 0.11 mm, and the nominal thickness of the laminates was 3 mm. The three types of specimens had the following stacking sequences: $[0]_{26}$, $[0/90]_{6s}$ and $[\pm 45]_{6s}$. A precrack was formed prior

to curing by inserting a 12 μm thick Telfon film in the mid-plane on one edge of the laminates. The initial crack length a_0 was 20 mm. All the specimens were examined by x-ray and ultrasonic c-scanning for quality control.

The critical interlaminar fracture toughness in the separation mode (mode I) G_{IC} was determined by the double cantilever beam (DCB) method. A special holder was designed so that the antilevers on the specimen were held by the grips of a INSTRON 1195 testing machine and a load was applied. The specimen was 24 mm wide and 200 mm long. The interlaminar fracture testing in the shear mode (mode II) G_{IIC} was measured by the end notched flexure (ENF) method. It was essentially a three point flexure loading measurement. The specimen was 20 mm wide and 60 mm long. In both tests, the load (P) versus displacement (δ) curves were traced on a chart recorder. For mode I, δ was the opening displacement while for mode II, δ was the bending displacement of the middle point of the beam. When the load reached a critical value P_c (also denoted by P_1) the precrack (a_0) grew and the increase in crack length a was measured. Then the load was reduced to zero. This procedure was repeated many times. Each crack extension was measured by a travelling microscope and photographs were taken using a WILD M3 long focal distance microscope. From the above data, G_{IC} and G_{IIC} can be calculated. Small DCB and ENF specimens were also tested in a S570 HITACHI scanning electron microscope (SEM). The dynamic propagation of interlaminar delamination and interface damage were observed and recorded in-situ.

3. INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS DATA REDUCTION AND ANALYSIS

The interlaminar fracture toughness is characterized by the energy release rate G_c . The compliance method, area method and LEFM polynomial form were used for the calculation of G_c .

3.1 Mode I testing

Compliance Method G_c is given by:

$$G_c = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dc}{da} \quad (1)$$

where b is the width of the specimen.

From beam analysis in plane stress,

$$c = \frac{2a^3}{3EI} \quad (2)$$

where E is the elastic modulus and I is the moment of inertia.

Substitution of Equation (2) into Equation (1) leads to

$$G_{IC} = \frac{P_c^2 a^2}{bEI} \quad (3)$$

Area Method By definition,

$$G_c = - \frac{1}{b} \left(\frac{dU}{da} \right) \quad (4)$$

where U is the total energy in the body. When the load-displacement curves for the cracked specimens exhibit a linear elastic response, the change in U due to crack extension from a to (a + Δa) is simply the area between the loading and unloading curves. Thus G_{Ic} is given by

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{1}{2b(\Delta a)} [P_1 \delta_2 - P_2 \delta_1] \quad (5)$$

LEFM Polynomial Form The stress intensity factor (K) and energy release rate (G) can be calculated from the following expressions⁽⁶⁾:

$$K_{Ic} = \frac{4P_c}{bh^{3/2}} (3a^2 + 3.84 ha + 1.22 h^2)^{1/2}$$

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{K_{Ic}^2}{E} + \frac{P_c^2}{bvS'} \quad (6)$$

where h is one half of the specimen thickness, v is the shear moduli, and $S' = 5/6 \times$ cross sectional area of the beam.

3.2 Mode II testing

Compliance Method By conjugate beam analysis

$$c = c_o \left(1 + \frac{3a^3}{2L^3} \right) + c_s \quad (7)$$

where L is the span between the central loading pin and the outer support pins, $c_o = L^3/6EI$ is the compliance of the reference specimen with no delamination (a = 0) and c_s is the contribution of the shear stresses to the overall compliance. Neglecting c_s and substituting Equation (7) into Equation (1) yields the expression for G_{IIc}

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{9a^2 P_c^2 c}{2b(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \quad (8)$$

LEFM Polynomial Form K_{IIc} and G_{IIc} are given by:

$$K_{IIc} = \frac{3P_c a}{2bh^{3/2}} \quad (9)$$

$$G_{IIc} = \frac{K_{IIc}^2}{E} \quad (10)$$

The above results are obtained from linear analyses. It has been shown⁽⁷⁾ that for the worst case (large debond length at critical load), the difference in the computed compliances from linear and nonlinear analyses is only 5%.

The experimental results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Interlaminar fracture toughness of T300/MBMI laminates

specimen lay-up	G_{Ic} (J/m^2)				G_{IIc} (J/m^2)		
	compliance method	area method	Poly-nominal form	average	compliance method	poly-nominal form	average
$[0]_{26}$	307	305	356	323	739	814	777
$[0/90]_{6s}$	171	153	189	171	414	460	437
$[\pm 45]_{6s}$	153	110	132	132	410	554	482

The agreement between the G_c values obtained from different methods are reasonable. For the $[\pm 45]$ specimens, the delamination propagation paths are irregular, thereby leading to more scattered G_c values. The average G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} values for the T300/MBMI $[0]$ specimen are $323 J/m^2$ and $777 J/m^2$, which are, respectively, 1 fold and 0.5 fold higher than those of T300/epoxy laminates ($G_{Ic} \approx 100 - 200 J/m^2$, $G_{IIc} \approx 400 - 560 J/m^2$)⁽⁸⁾. This implies that the modified BMI matrix has a considerable toughening effect. The G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} values of the $[0]$ laminates are higher than those of the $[0/90]$ ply and $[\pm 45]$ ply laminates. This arises because there are fiber bridging in $[0]$ laminates, and the interlaminar cracks in the multi-directional laminates propagate not only in the precrack plane, but also in the 45° or 90° plies.

4. CRACK PROPAGATION

Mode I interlaminar crack growth of the 0° laminates is along the precrack plane in 0° direction (Fig. 1). The critical delamination propagation is shown more clearly in the high-magnification picture (Fig. 2). Fibers are pulled out behind the crack tip. A few fibers are bridging the crack and subsequently broken by bending.

Fig. 1 Mode I interlaminar crack propagation in $[0]$ specimen

Fig. 2 Mode I critical delamination propagation in $[0]$ specimen

The interlaminar crack growth in the multi-directional laminate involves the splitting of the crack tip into primary crack and secondary crack, with the latter branching off the precrack plane. For the $[\pm 45]_{6S}$ laminate, the crack grows along the horizontal precrack, then turns 45° through the thickness of a 45° ply (Fig. 3). For the $[0/90]_{6S}$ laminate, the primary crack grows along the precrack plane first, then one subcrack branches through the thickness of a 90° ply (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3 Mode I interlaminar crack propagation in $[\pm 45]$ specimen

Fig. 4 Mode I main crack and sub-crack in $[0/90]$ specimen

In mode II, the crack pattern of the unidirectional specimen was found to be essentially the same as in mode I, and the interference between cracks was minor (Fig. 5a). However, the damage zones in multi-directional specimen are larger due to the larger load bearing area. Take the $[0/90]_{6S}$ cross-plyed specimen as an example. Under critical flexure loading P_c , the

Fig. 5a Mode II crack propagation in $[0/90]$ specimen

Fig. 5b Mode II main crack and fiber broken in $[0/90]$ specimen

main crack grows in the precrack plane. With an increase in load, subcracks occurred and propagated. Transverse cracks through the 90° ply and delamination at the 0-90 interfaces was observed in the neighboring plies (Fig. 5a). Fig. 5b,c shows that there are shear cracks in the matrix and fibers are broken by bending. However, there is good adhesion between the fibers and the matrix (Fig. 5c).

Thus, the mechanisms of interlaminar crack growth involve crack-tip splitting, fiber pull-out behind the crack tip, some fiber-bridging as well as interface debonding.

Fig. 5c Shear cracks in 90° ply

5. TOUGHENING MECHANISMS OF GRAPHITE/MBMI COMPOSITES

The interlaminar fracture toughness G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} of T300/MBMI are higher than those of T300/epoxy composites by factors of 2 and 1.5, respectively. This reflects a significant toughening effect, which arises from the microstructure and properties of the modified bismaleimide matrix. This new MBMI system is prepared by co-reacting oligomers of a bismaleimide and PES. Upon curing, a crosslinked polymer structure is formed which has excellent thermal and mechanical properties. The elongation to break is 2.2%, the fracture work is 2381 N-m, the tensile strength and modulus are 65.6 MPa and 3.5 GPa, respectively. The glass transition temperature (T_g) is 278°C. All of these values are substantially higher than those of epoxy and other BMIs^(3,4). The transverse tensile strength σ_T and interlaminar shear strength τ_{ILSS} of T300/MBMI are higher than those of T300/epoxy by factors of 2 and 1.25, respectively⁽⁵⁾. This indicates that the adhesive strength and toughness of the T300 fiber-MBMI matrix interface are better than those of T300/epoxy.

SEM fractography also supports the above argument. The interface bonding of T300/MBMI (Fig. 6) is superior to that of T300/epoxy (Fig. 7). The MBMI matrix is uniformly adhered to the surface of the fibers, thereby providing adequate protection. Many thermoplastic particles (size about 3 μm) of the matrix are adhering to the fiber. Therefore there are more matrix cracking and energy consumption when delamination occurs. As shown in Fig. 8, shear bands are formed under loading. The shear hackles of T300/MBMI are dense and irregular, but in the epoxy matrix the shear hackles are flat and fewer in number.

Fig. 6 Interface state of T300/MBMI Fig. 7 Interface state of T300/epoxy

The presence of shear band and plastic deformation lead to a delay in matrix cracking and interface debonding. As a result, the interlaminar fracture toughness becomes higher. Because plastic deformation is more significant in the ENF specimens than the DCB specimens, G_{IIC} is higher than G_{IC} .

From dynamic bending failure fractography the delamination and transverse cracking of the ± 45 layers in the T300/epoxy laminate (Fig. 9) are more serious than those in the T300/MBMI laminate (Fig. 10). The interlaminar bonding in the T300/MBMI laminate is rather strong and the transverse cracks are fine and fewer in number.

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

Interface shear band
of T300/MBMI

Dynamic shear failure
of T300/epoxy laminate

Dynamic shear failure
of T300/MBMI laminate

The primary cause of toughening is the presence of plastic deformation and various irregular shear hackles in the MBMI matrix. The secondary mechanism is a satisfactory interface adhesion. Both of these contribute to an increase in energy dissipation.

6. CONCLUSION

The interlaminar fracture toughnesses G_{IC} and G_{IIC} of T300 graphite fiber reinforced modified bismaleimide composites are higher than those of T300/epoxy composites by factors of 2 and 1.5, respectively.

This toughening results from the increase in matrix toughness and improvement of interface bonding. In MBMI composites, there is much more disorder in the arrangement and shape of the shear bands and hackles under loading, thereby leading to an increase in the energy release when debonding occurs.

In general, the interlaminar fracture toughness of [0] laminates is higher than those of [0/90] and [± 45] laminates, because there are fibers bridging the crack in [0] laminates. In multi-directional laminates, the delamination propagates not only along the precrack direction but also in other plies.

Interlaminar fracture studies in a scanning electron microscope allow the in situ observation and recording of the dynamic propagation of delamination and damage of fiber-matrix interface. This is an effective approach for elucidating the toughening mechanism of modified BMI.

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